

Understanding Women Empowerment Through Fishery Activities: A Case of Paschim Medinipur District of West Bengal

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Abstract: It explores the women empowerment and its challenges by the fishery activities in Paschim Medinipur district of West Bengal. It is focusing on socio-economic, political and psychological empowerment of women and challenges. Surveying 100 women, it highlights moderate level empowerment, with high psychological and social status, but low political empowerment. It enhance women's income, confidence and resource access, though they have some challenges such as limited training, patriarchal barriers and lack of awareness, which indicates structural inequalities and call for policy interventions to enhance political inclusion and economic stability.

Keywords: women empowerment, fishery activities, fisherwomen, Paschim Medinipur

1. INTRODUCTION

Empowerment of women is an important aspect of gender's studies, as it promotes gender equality, economic freedom and social justice. We know that in India, fisherwomen make significant contributions to livelihood, yet their role is often underestimated. Among the different field of livelihoods, fisheries one of them which is create opportunity to increase the socio-economic, political and psychological position of women. Further it serves as an important source of income generation and food security for many rural families. Especially women, who are from marginal sections. However, their contributions are largely informal, weak paid as well as they are being faced multiple challenges. Despite these challenges, fisheries activities enable women to get access to the resources, create confidence and move towards self-sustenance. That's why, the researcher attempts to explore how the fishery activities contribute to women empowerment and how many challenges they are being face in Paschim Medinipur.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of the literature is essential part to understand the level of women empowerment in Paschim Medinipur in fisheries, to identify gaps and to guide research effectively. That's why the researcher has reviewed five literatures, which has mentioned below-

De Beauvoir has discussed about woman in her book "Second Sex", where she challenges the idea of womanhood, and she says that it is determined by biology not by the society. That's why, in this context she made a remark, "One is not born, but rather becomes, a woman". Further, Beauvoir argues that women are considered as "other" in relation to men, which denies the subjectivity and autonomy of women (De Beauvoir 14).

Mandal has conducted a study on "Concept and Types of Women Empowerments", he has described some important characteristic of women empowerment these are- what is empowerment, types of empowerments, method of empowerment, condition of empowerment etc. Here, the author highlighted that women empowerment is new concept from the second half of the twenty centuries. It em-

phasized the global relevance to scholars at the university, noting the myriad challenges women face in society and advocating for spaces that enhance their sustainable development (Mandal, 17-30).

Reshi and Sudha has conducted a study on “*Women Empowerment: A Literature Review*”, where they have described few special features of women empowerment, these are concept of empowerment, historical evolution of women empowerment, challenges of empowerment and the role of government, NGOs and private sector etc. but the authors has mainly focus on women empowerment, they have said that it is process of development where women can control their life. And also, they have said that we have to give them access of education, healthcare, employment opportunities, and political representation. It indicates that all kind of barriers which are prevent women from achieving all kind of development (Reshi & Sudha, 1353).

Weeratunge et al. have conducted a study on “*Small-scale Fisheries Through the Wellbeing Lens*”. This article uses a good structure in small-scale fisheries, examining how social, economic and environmental factors affect the livelihoods of the fisheries-based community. In order to achieve sustainable fisheries, it indicates the significance of women's role and obstacles to consider. (Weeratunge et al., 255-79).

Jacob et al. conducted a study on “*Challenging Traditional Gender Roles– Women Empowerment through Ornamental Fish Farming*”, where it is reflects that ornamental fish culture are gaining immense popularity all over the world. In earlier days, it used to cultivate ornamental fish as hobby but present time ornamental fish is a becoming business. But in India, having an enabling environment for ornamental fisheries can generate income and employment for women, through which women empowerment can flourish. As the participation of women in fishing sectors will help the society to eliminate gender inequality through this ornamental agriculture, it also helps to improve the quality of life of women in different countries, states, and villages. As women entrepreneurs, their contribution to the national gross productivity is increasing day by day. And women are creating their own employment, thereby creating awareness of economic freedom for their children and other women (Jacob, Rajan, & Mathew, 29-35).

3. RESEARCH GAP

We have reviewed five literatures related to this research, namely books and articles that are informative and important to me. However, none of these reviews are directly related to proposed study. However, it is important to note that this contemporary study (Understanding Women Empowerment through Fishery Activities: A Case of Paschim Medinipur District of West Bengal) has special significance, so the researcher has been focused not only on women empowerment level, but he has been focused on how they are being empowered in every aspect of society. Also, the researcher is trying to understand their empowerment trend and what kind of obstacles they are facing. Because of which, there is a justification for this proposed study.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.(A) Objective of this Study

- 1) To examine the level of women empowerment through fishery activities in Paschim Medinipur district.
- 2) Which kinds of problems are emerging Infront of the fisherwomen and how they will overcome these problems?

4.(B) Area of the Study

This study has conducted in Paschim Medinipur district. It is (also known as Midnapore West) one of the oldest districts of the West Bengal. which is situated in the south-western part of West Bengal, which has 21blocks across 3 Sub-division.

4.(C) Methods of this Study

This proposed study has followed Descriptive and Exploratory Research with Quantitative and Qualitative method to Understanding Women Empowerment through Fishery Activities: A Case of Paschim Medinipur District of West Bengal.

4.(E) Data collection

The necessary data has collected both from primary as well as secondary sources. For primary data, the researcher has gone through extensive field study with Interviews with structure questionnaires. For secondary data the researcher has visited, collect governmental office, libraries, review the books, articles etc.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

5.(A) Demographic Profile of the Fisherwomen

Graph No 1. Age Oriented Participation of Women in Paschim Medinipur

It shows that largest participants of women (41.50%) fall within the 40-50 age group. The next highest group is 29-39, which there are 31.50 percent women. In contrast, the youngest age group is comprised with 9% women (18-28). The lower participants age groups (50-60) is comprised with 13.50% women and 60-70 age groups is comprised with 4.50% women. The synthesized percentage trend is 80% fisherwomen are belonging from 29-50 years age groups.

Table No 1. Educational Qualification of Fisherwomen

Educational Qualification Women	Frequency (N=100)	Percentage %	Cumulative %
Illiterate	20	20.00%	20.00%
Class 1st – 10th	67	67.00%	87.00%
Class 11th -12th	7	7.00%	94.00%
B.A 1st -3rd Years	5	5.00%	99.00%
M.A 1st -2nd Years	1	1.00%	100.00%
Total Women 100	100	100.00%	100.00%

This table highlights the educational profile of fisherwomen. It reflects a significant tendency to limited education among employed in fishery activities. The

majority, with 67% (67 respondents) integrated has completed education up to class (1-10) one to ten. A significant 20% of the respondents have completely illiterate. High level education significantly presents that only 7% women have completed class eleven to twelve (11th-12th) and 5%, 1% women have completed their bachelor and master's degree.

Stock No.1. Caste Oriented Fisherwomen Participation

Caste of Women	Frequency (N=100)	Percentage %	Cumulative %
GEN	23	23.00%	23.00%
OBC	19	19.00%	42.00%
SC	44	44.00%	86.00%
ST	14	14.00%	100.00%
Total Women	200	100.00%	100.00%

It highlights the caste oriented of fisherwomen participation. The largest ratio of respondents belongs to the scheduled caste (SC) section, whose accounting is 44% (44 women). The general caste women are 23% of the total samples (23 women), and other hand, other backward class (OBC) is at 20 % (20 women). The Schedule Tribe (ST) forms 13% (13 women).

3. (B) FISHERY ACTIVITIES RELATED PROFILE OF WOMEN IN PASCHIM MEDINIPUR DISTRICT

Table No 2. Types of Fishery Activities

The data provides insight into the types of fishery activities adopted by women. Out of a total of 100 women surveyed, the majority 45.5% women are involved solely in fish selling. The next largest group contains 27% women, who are involved in both selling and production. Production alone engages 25% women. Meanwhile, a small-scale minority is actively involved in catching and selling (1.5%) and only one woman (1%) is solely focusing in catch the fish.

Table No 3. Duration of Work

Duration of Works	Frequency (N=100)	Percentage %	Cumulative %
01-10 Years	63	63.00%	63.00%
11-20 Years	20	20.00%	83.50%
21-30 Years	12	12.00%	95.00%
31-40 Years	5	5.00%	100.00%
Total Women	100	100.00%	100.00%

It presents the duration of work among 100 women involved in the fishery

related activities. The majority, 63 women (63%) have been working for 1 to 10 years, following it, 20 women (20%) have 11 to 20 years of work experience, and a small section, 12 women (12%) have been on the filed for 21 to 30 years, while only 5 women (5%) have 31 to 40 years of work experience.

Pie No 2. Fishery Activities' Related Ownership

It indicates the fishery activities related ownership profile, most of the women, 64% women are engaged in individual ownership, Group ownership accounts for 30%, and a small-scale, 6% women are involved in both individual and group ownership.

Table No 6. Stability of Activities

Stability of Activities	Frequency (N=100)	Percentage %	Cumulative %
Permanent	83	83.00%	83.00%
Temporary	17	17.00%	100.00%
Total Women 100	100	100.00%	100.00%

It presents the stability of activities among 100 women engaged in certain occupations. It shows a huge majority 83 women (83.50%) are involved in permanent activities, while only 17 women (17%) are actively engaged in temporary activities. It suggests the more stable and continuous form of employment or economic activities in women.

4. (C) LEVEL OF WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH FISHERY ACTIVITIES IN PASCHIM MEDINIPUR DISTRICT

Scatter No 1. Economic Empowerment Level of Women

It categorized women into three levels of empowerment (low, moderate, and high) based on the survey of 100 participants. Most women fall under moderate empowerment (56.5%). The high empowerment group consists of 25% out of the 100 women. In contrast, low empowerment is seen within 18.5% of the total respondents, which is representing with minimal access to economic resources. This

distribution emphasizes a Moderate Level of Empowerment. The presence of a significant group with low empowerment suggests uninterrupted problems such as limited employment, low income or lack of control over financial.

Table No 5. Social Empowerment Level of Women in Paschim Medinipur District

Social Empowerment Level of Women	Total Women	Percentage %
Low Empowerment	13	13
Moderate Empowerment	43	43
High Empowerment	44	44
Total Women	100	100

It presents a clear image of Social Empowerment among the women in Paschim Medinipur district. Out of the 100 women surveyed, most of the women (44%) fall into the high-level empowerment category. A positive sign is a moderate empowerment group, which comprises 43% out of 100 women. Nevertheless, 13% of women are classified as having low social empowerment, it suggests that some females are marginalized or lack of access to important opportunities and resources.

Table No 6. Political Empowerment Level of Women in Paschim Medinipur District

Political Empowerment Level of Women	Total Women	Percentage %
Low Empowerment	52	52
Moderate Empowerment	48	48
High Empowerment	0	0
Total Women	100	100%

The data set describes the level of Political Empowerment of women in Paschim Medinipur district. Surveyed among the 100 respondents, 52% women are at a low-level empowerment and remaining 48% respondents shows the moderate level empowerment. It shows that even though some progress towards involvement is present, the full political empowerment for women remains an important challenge in the region.

Table No 7 Psychological Empowerment Level of Women in Paschim Medinipur District

Psychological Empowerment Level of Women	Total Women	Percentage %
Low Empowerment	1	1
Moderate Empowerment	19	19
High Empowerment	80	80
Total Women	100	100%

The table provides an overview of Psychological Empowerment Level among fisherwomen in Paschim Medinipur district. Out of the 100 women surveyed, the majority of the women (80%) fall under high empowerment level. A small section of women (19%) has reported that they have gain moderate level empowerment and significantly, only 1 woman (1%) are identified with low empowerment.

Table No 8. Overall Empowerment Level of Women in Paschim Medinipur District

Overall Women Empowerment Level	Total Women	Percentage %
Low Empowerment	4	4
Moderate Empowerment	90	90
High Empowerment	6	6
Total Women	100	100%

The level of Overall Empowerment of women in Paschim Medinipur district reveals that large majority women gain a moderate empowerment experience. In the survey out of 100 women, 91 (90%) women fall into the Moderate level Empowerment section. A small section of women (4%,) reported low empowerment and in contrast, 6 women (6%) have been reported as highly empowered. This distribution suggests that serious deprivation is rare, and empowerment initiatives have reached most women, very few people still have achieved the highest level of autonomy and influence.

Conclusion

The study on women in Paschim Medinipur district highlights that fishery activities play an important role by encouraging women's empowerment, economic freedom, social recognition and psychological confidence. However, the level of overall empowerment remains unequal in the aspect of social, economic, political and psychological. Though they are socially, economically and psychologically empowered but politically marginalized from the mainstream of society. Despite these achievements, they have faced multiple obstacles, such as—

- Low and inconsistent income
- Limited training opportunities
- Weak awareness about welfare facilities
- Patriarchal control
- Gender bias
- Seasonal employment
- Limited education

From a feminist theory perspective- especially socialist and liberal feminism, these findings show how structural patriarchy and bureaucratic barriers restrict women's full emancipation, even when women contribute substantially to the economy and household welfare. It addresses income insecurity, redistribute resource and it ensuring genuine political participation align with feminist demands for dismantling gendered structure and achieving equality for fisherwomen in both private and public life.

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